

From Grey to WDM-Enabled White-LED VLC:

WDM Operation of High-Flux Phosphor-Converted White LEDs for Joint Illumination and Visible-Light Communication

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Abstract:

The WDM operation of phosphor-converted high-flux white-LED emission is introduced for VLC applications that fuse illumination and communication. 100 Mb/s data transmission is facilitated at a penalty of 1.5dB with respect to single-channel operation. Moreover, dual-drive 200Mb/s PAM4 operation and simultaneous signaling/data transmission is demonstrated.

1. Introduction

Visible light communication (VLC) is an attractive method for data exchange by virtue of its robustness to electro-magnetic interference and its use of unregulated optical spectrum [1]. Even though impressive data rates beyond 25 Gb/s have been achieved through laser-sourced lighting and communication systems [2], the abundance of light emitting diode (LED) technology in the field of lighting, as emphasized through widely used white LEDs, provides a convenient opportunity to seamlessly and cost-efficiently integrate VLC functionality. In contrast to white micro-LEDs that offer a high bandwidth yet at a highly limited optical output [3], high-flux LEDs designed for the purpose of lighting do not resemble ideal optical transmitters: Their large active die sizes introduce bandwidth restrictions while the generated white spectrum is often a result of a phosphor-converted blue pump light, thus additionally resulting in slow red-shifted components. As a way to mitigate these effects, earlier works have focused on equalization [4-9] and additional blue-filtered reception [6-9] to accomplish data rates of up to 3 Gb/s.

While earlier works have focused on “grey” VLC links with one transmitter and one receiver or wavelength division multiplexed (WDM) LED emitters and photoreceivers [10-13], this work investigates the WDM operation of phosphor-converted white LEDs for 100-Mb/s transmission over blue WDM channels. Besides, dual-drive PAM4 operation at 200 Mb/s and simultaneous low-/high-speed data transmission will be shown.

2. Spectral Multiplexing of White-LED Emission

The spectrum of white LEDs is determined by its blue die source and its phosphorescence, whereas the weighting in blue and yellow/red components determines the correlated color temperature (CCT). Unlike natural sunlight, the blue source of white LEDs emits in a spectrally confined region. Figure 1 discusses the spectral characteristics of the neutral-white LEDs. The four evaluated commercial LEDs, denoted A-D in Fig. 1a, feature a luminous flux of >130 lm and a CCT in the vicinity of 4000K. Even though the LEDs have a similar CCT, their blue sources show distinctive spectral features, as evidenced from the overall white-light spectrum in Fig. 1b. When attributing a WDM band to the blue region, the LED sources can be allocated to different channels if the 10-nm WDM grid of Fig. 1c is considered. Given the resulting coupling T_λ to these constituent WDM channels, which is summarized in Fig. 2a, pairs of LEDs can be identified to facilitate WDM operation. For example, pair B-A leads to a maximal RF crosstalk level of -13.9 dB, as probed through reception of RF tones at 50 MHz (Fig. 2a).

Fig. 1: (a) Chromaticity and (b) spectral emission of employed white LEDs. (c) Allocation of blue LED source to WDM channels.

Even though the practical adoption of such a WDM grid might appear as a complexity burden at first glance, the involved blue-filtering is an actual necessity to accomplish reasonable electro-optic white-LED bandwidths

through suppression of the slow red-shifted phosphorus components in the received optical spectrum. This response flattening is shown in Fig. 2b for white LED ‘D’. Without optical filter, the electro-optic response drops quickly and surpasses its 3-dB bandwidth at 0.44 MHz (\diamond). When adopting blue-filtering at 450 nm, the roll-off smoothens. However, the modulation bandwidth of 3.8 MHz (\blacklozenge) remains too small. When applying frequency response flattening through analogue equalization (see Fig. 3, α) integrated in the RF drive path of the LED, the bandwidth can be vastly extended to 105 MHz (\bullet), which suffices 100 Mb/s transmission. The unfiltered LED (\diamond) would have required 15 dB of extra pre-emphasis to reach the same bandwidth. Moreover, there is no significant impact on the frequency response profile when altering the WDM channel, apart from the expected change in peak magnitude due to the tilt in the spectral profile of the LED emission across several WDM channels.

Even though this analogue pre-emphasis allows to flatten the highly tilted response between low and high frequencies, the intrinsic response of the LED needs to be accounted for when accounting for the RF budget. While a saturation power of up to 30 dBm is feasible for the RF driver, the poor conversion efficiency of the white LEDs at high frequencies limits the accomplishable modulation index to very low values, which directly translates into reception penalties due to the limited optical modulation amplitude (OMA). The example shown as inset in Fig. 3 indicates that the typical modulation index features a value of less than 0.1.

Fig. 2: (a) LED emission in WDM channels. (b) Electro-optic response of white LED after blue-filtering and equalization.

3. White-LED Broadcast & Select WDM VLC Link

Figure 3 further presents the experimental setup for 100 Mb/s WDM-enabled on-off keyed (OOK) VLC transmission over response-flattened white LEDs. Two of these LEDs are paired through a broadband beamsplitter (BS) and illuminate a blue-enhanced APD+TIA receiver with a responsivity of 32 A/W at 450 nm. In order to evaluate the WDM concept, an optical bandpass filter with bandwidth $\delta\lambda$ is inserted before the APD to select spectral components within one of the aforementioned WDM channels. A neutral density (ND) filter sets the optical budget (OB) for the lab-scale 3.2 m VLC link between white LED emitters and APD receiver, which further utilize 2" optics for the purpose of collimation and light collection. The received signal is forwarded to bit error ratio (BER) testing and also digitized for further signal analysis. A second, unfiltered APD+TIA receiver is additionally employed to investigate the simultaneous signaling and data transmission over the VLC link.

Fig. 3: Experimental setup to evaluate white-LED WDM VLC and integrated signaling through dual-drive LED emitter.

4. WDM Reception and Integration of Signalling

The BER performance for single-channel transmission at 450 nm is presented in Fig. 4a for various spectral cut-off frequencies due to blue filtering with variable filter bandwidth $\delta\lambda$. Two effects can be noticed: First, an increased filter width leads to an error floor as it passes the slower red components (Fig. 1b). This applies for a

cut-off of 550 nm (◆) and higher. Second, too narrow filtering at $\delta\lambda = 10$ nm, equivalent to a low cut-off of 455 nm (▲), causes a high loss in optical power, as summarized in Fig. 4b. This filtering loss, which – as expected – amounts to 6.8 dB between $\delta\lambda = 10$ nm (▲) and 50-nm (●), translates into a reduced OB that can be addressed for the VLC link. As Fig. 4b shows, the optimum performance is found for a cut-off at 475 nm ($\delta\lambda = 50$ nm). However, this filter bandwidth is too broad to accommodate multiple WDM channels, meaning that WDM operation with the given white-LED spectra will be naturally bound to a decrease in OB.

Figure 4c reports the BER performance under such WDM operation, for which comparison is further made with single-channel transmission (□,◇,△,○) using the same blue-filtering setting at $\delta\lambda = 10$ nm. When pairing LEDs B and A at two adjacent WDM channels at 440 nm (◆) and 450 nm (▲), WDM crosstalk leads to a penalty of 5.8 dB (◆,◇) and 4.4 dB (▲,△) at a BER of 10^{-3} with respect to single-channel transmission at the respective wavelengths. When increasing the spacing between the two WDM wavelengths to 30 nm, meaning to operate a LED pair B-C at 430 nm (■) and 460 nm (●) while skipping two WDM channels in between them, this penalty reduces to 1.5 and 1.1 dB. This proves that two-channel WDM operation is in principle compatible with the spectral configuration of white high-flux LEDs.

Fig. 4: (a) BER for various blue filters and (b) compatible optical budget. (c) BER under WDM operation for two white-LED pairs.

Moreover, the dual-drive operation of a white LED emitter is evaluated in Fig. 5a for operation at the 450-nm channel. By differentially driving anode and cathode of the white LED emitter (Fig. 3, δ), the OMA can be doubled, which leads to an increase in supported OB by 6.1 dB. On top of this, the dual-drive configuration enables PAM4 modulation. Figure 5a includes the BER for 200 Mb/s PAM4 transmission (▲) after off-line multi-level symbol slicing. A BER below the FEC limit at 10^{-3} is accomplished for an OB of 3.1 dB. With this, the dual-drive emitter allows for a rate-adaptive VLC transmission, without deviating from a simple two-level electrical driving scheme.

Finally, the dual-drive scheme has been adopted to facilitate high-speed (HS) 100 Mb/s VLC transmission with simultaneous low-speed (LS) signaling at 5 Mb/s. For this configuration that re-uses the same optical spectrum to convey two signals, the HS OOK signal has been 8B10B-coded, resulting in a line rate of 125 Mb/s. Reception is conducted with two distinct VLC receivers (Fig. 3), for which only that detecting the HS data applies blue-filtering at 450 nm, $\delta\lambda = 10$ nm, while the other detects the full white LED spectrum, without filtering loss. Figure 5b presents a representative unfiltered time-domain signal and RF spectrum as detected by the HS receiver, showing the impact of simultaneous LS signaling on the HS data transmission.

The corresponding BER performance for HS and LS VLC transmission is discussed in Fig. 5c as a function of the ratio ζ between the OMAs for the LS and HS signals. The Q-factor of the LS signaling directly depends on the choice for its OMA_{LS} (○). There is little degradation due to simultaneous HS data transmission (●) since low-pass filter can cater for its suppression. The reception performance for exclusive HS data transmission shows that

the additional extension in data signal bandwidth due to line coding is leading to a BER floor at 1.3×10^{-5} (\square) as the flat electro-optic response of the blue-filtered white LED is exceeded. Simultaneous HS + LS data transmission introduces a large penalty on the HS data reception (\blacksquare), leading to a BER beyond 10^{-2} for a setting of $\zeta = 0.7$. However, the cross-talk from simultaneous LS data transmission can be effectively suppressed when applying high-pass filtering with a cut-on at 4 MHz (\blacklozenge). The BER then approaches the performance for exclusive HS data transmission, while a small penalty dependent on the OMA of the LS data signal resides. A Q-factor beyond 6 for the 5 Mb/s LS data signal and a BER below 10^{-3} for the net-100 Mb/s HS signal can be jointly accomplished (Ξ) for $\zeta = 0.8$, meaning that the optimal OMA for LS signaling is slightly lower than that for HS data.

Fig. 5: (a) BER for dual-drive LED operation. (b) LS signaling integrated with HS data transmission, (c) HS BER and LS Q-factor.

5. Conclusions

WDM operation has been introduced for white LEDs. 100 Mb/s transmission at two blue WDM channels proves the compatibility of commercial high-flux emitters for joint illumination and VLC. Moreover, the dual-drive operation of these LEDs has been shown to facilitate a higher OB or PAM4, which can be beneficial for rate/distance adaptive scenarios. Finally, simultaneous LS/HS signalling with asymmetric data rates can cater for highly varying traffic demands. All these modes involving white LEDs can be beneficial in scenarios where different optical transmitters are flexibly linking with multi-element VLC receivers.

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